

HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS

conCEPTION

SAFETY EVIDENCE ECOSYSTEM

What is the goal of 'Moeders van Morgen'?

Research has shown that around 80% of pregnant women use at least one medicine during pregnancy. In daily practice you'll face the problem, as a healthcare professional, that information about medicine use during pregnancy is often limited available.

When you have questions about medicine use during pregnancy, you can visit our website for more information in our knowledge bank, or contact us by telephone for a consult (073-64 69 702).

Besides, there is a high need of more extensive information in this field of research. To reduce the burden for you as a healthcare professional, pregnant women can fill in the 6 online questionnaires by themselves.

Data protection of participants

Moeders van Morgen attaches great importance to privacy protection of your clients and to safely maintain personal data. We only do this in accordance with the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Who can participate and what do we ask of participants?

All pregnant women can participate. In this way, we can get a complete picture of daily practice, choices that have been made during pregnancy and if these choices are safe. This information provides insight into what medicines are used, prescribed medicines as well as over-the-counter products (including folic acid and vitamins), homeopathic products and vaccines.

There are only two requirements: participants need to be at least 18 years old and need to master the Dutch language. A pregnant woman can subscribe for the questionnaires at any time of gestation during pregnancy, but preferably as early in the pregnancy as possible.

Times of sending questionnaires:

Promotion material – toolbox

All our promotion materials, including for online use, can be found in the toolbox on the website. You can find and order the toolbox by e-mail (info@moedersvanmorgen.nl) or by telephone (0031-73-64 69 700).

What can you do as a healthcare professional?

You can contribute to inform your clients about Moeders van Morgen. For example, you can send the invitation e-mail (read more below) and provide flyers.

We experienced that around 30% of women receiving an invitation e-mail from a healthcare professional, is going to participate in our research. Women only receiving a flyer participated for 6% only.

Healthcare professional account

You can invite pregnant women by requesting an account for healthcare professionals by sending us an e-mail:

info@moedersvanmorgen.nl. We'll provide you with a login name and password, so you can login on the website

www.moedersvanmorgen.nl, in order to send an invitation by filling in the name and e-mail address of the participant. The participant will receive an invitation, signed by the healthcare professional. Finally, it's up to the woman to decide if she wants to participate or not.

In the Netherlands, sending an invitation for healthcare professionals is also possible for midwives working with 'Orfeus' or 'Vrumun', digital applications with medical data of the participant. Participants will automatically receive an invitation by e-mail to apply for Moeders van Morgen.

